

**POSSIBILITIES OF USING ELEMENTS OF ROBOTICS IN TEACHING PHYSICS:
INTERDISCIPLINARY CONTINUITY IN STEM EDUCATION**

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Abstract

The STEM direction is of great importance in the modern education system, as it is aimed at preparing students for the modern job market, developing creativity and critical thinking skills. The integration of physics and computer science disciplines, in particular the elements of robotics in physics, plays an important role in educational programs. Mastering both areas for schoolchildren and students will contribute to their success in research and engineering work in the future. The purpose of this study is to make it easier for students to understand complex physical concepts and increase their interest through the use of robotics in teaching physics, the effective implementation of the continuity of STEM disciplines. In the course of the study, an analysis was carried out on scientific publications in reliable sources based on the method of qualitative design, pedagogical control works based on qualitative research in the educational process. The use of elements of robotics in teaching physics made it possible to make the learning process interactive and practical. This research has been/was/is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP22784343).

Keywords: STEM education, STEM project learning, interdisciplinary continuity, robotics.

Introduction

The use of STEM Technologies prepares students to be successful in the technological and scientific fields in the future. The relationship between STEM and robotics allows for a comprehensive education for students. Robotics combines all aspects of STEM education and allows students to acquire skills that will be used in real life. This method develops students' critical thinking, problem solving, and technical skills, as well as contributes to their success in the future. Through the connection of STEM and robotics, students apply theoretical knowledge in practice and understand the relationship between science and technology.

Domestic scientists D.Boyarinov, A.E.Samarina considered the potential of educational robotics in teacher training. The authors noted the importance of integrating innovative technologies into the educational process to improve the quality of Education. Organizational and pedagogical conditions for the training of students of pedagogical specialties in the field of educational robotics based on the multiplatform principle make it possible to personalize and activate the educational process of the future robotics teacher [1].

The theoretical and practical aspects of the use of robotics for education in teaching school-age children can be traced in the works of several scientists. R.F.Zúñiga Muñoz et al considers the methodology of the childprogramming method for teaching and educational robotics regulation. The authors emphasize the importance of effective methods of teaching programming for children, especially in the context of educational robotics. ChildProgramming is a way to learn

programming aimed at Children. It involves the use of intuitive and interactive methods that contribute to a better understanding and assimilation of the material [2].

The potential for the formation of students' creativity with the help of robotics is determined by foreign scientists B. Hendrik et al consider. The authors have developed a model of figured creativity based on the concept of learning through robotics. The model developed by the researchers includes the following structural components: problems of assembling robots, the use of creative methods for solving problems and assessing the creativity of students. The model developed by the authors has shown its effectiveness, offering a new approach to integrating technology into the educational process. The authors emphasize the need for additional research in this area to improve educational experience [3].

Although there are many advantages to using robotics in teaching physics, various problems can arise during its implementation. To solve these problems, it is important to provide financial support, improve the skills of teachers, make the curriculum more effective, provide technical support, comply with security measures and apply individual teaching methods. Through the implementation of these measures, robotics can be effectively used in teaching physics.

Research methods

The study used a design method (DBR) aimed at developing solutions used in specific educational environments and testing them in practice. This method is iterative in nature, that is, research and design go

through several cycles, and changes are made in each cycle based on the results obtained. The DBR method allows you to put theoretical knowledge into practice and develop a theory based on practical results. The design method is an innovative and integrative method aimed at solving problems in the field of Education. This method ensures a combination of theory and practice and helps to develop effective interventions aimed at improving the education system. Through the DBR method, researchers develop comprehensive and effective solutions aimed at solving specific problems, test and improve them in practice [4].

Also, methods for analyzing reliable articles were used to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of information.

Results and analyzes

From the results of the analysis of the literature, it can be seen that STEM interdisciplinary continuity

aims to develop the ability to think comprehensively, acquire practical skills, develop innovative thinking, and improve professional training. Students are formed the ability to see the relationship between different disciplines and solve complex problems, practical skills that can be applied in real life, the desire to make discoveries, implement new ideas, and readiness for work in technological and scientific fields that will be needed in the future.

STEM continuity in teaching individual subjects of physics allows students to demonstrate the relationship between the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering and mathematics and master them in a comprehensive manner. The following are the main aspects and examples of STEM continuity in teaching individual physics disciplines (Table 1).

Table 1.

STEM continuity in teaching individual physics disciplines				
Subject Of Physics	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics
1	2	3	4	5
Mechanics	Experiments: study of the movement of bodies and the influence of forces.	Measurement and analysis of movement using sensors (for example, accelerometer).	Assembly of robots and mechanisms and control of their movement.	Solving equations of motion, constructing graphs and analyzing data.
Heat and thermodynamics	Experiments to study thermal phenomena (thermal conductivity, convection).	The use of temperature sensors and thermal imaging.	Design and analysis of heating systems.	Mathematical description and calculation of thermodynamic processes.
Electricity and magnetism	Study of the properties of electric and magnetic fields.	Assembly and analysis of electrical circuits (Arduino, Raspberry Pi).	Design and manufacture of electrical devices.	Construction and calculation of a mathematical model of electrical circuits.
Optics	Conducting experiments on the refraction, reflection and dispersion of light.	The use of lasers and optical instruments.	Design and assembly of optical systems.	Mathematical description of the distribution of light.

STEM technologies allow students to test and understand physical theories in practice. Through tools such as Arduino and Lego robotics, for example, students can explore physical laws through specific examples. This method demonstrates the practical application of theoretical knowledge and increases students' interest in the educational process. STEM technologies

make the learning process interactive and visual. For example, simulations and virtual laboratories allow you to visualize physical phenomena (Figure 1). This makes it easier for students to understand complex concepts and promotes better assimilation of educational material.

Figure 1. Continuity between the STEM industry

In teaching the topic of movement of mechanics in a circle, you can demonstrate specific laws of motion using Lego robots. This helps students visualize their theoretical knowledge. Students themselves will be able to design and program robots, track their movements and analyze the results (Figure 2).

Students observe the movement of robots and conduct experiments, changing different parameters:

- Change the radius of the circle;
- Changing the speed of the robot;

- Calculation and control of the centripetal force.

Students collect data from each experiment and analyze the dependence of angular velocity and acceleration on the radius of the circle, the change in the centripetal force and its effect on the movement of the robot. Students also draw conclusions based on the results obtained, compare theoretical knowledge and practical results, and identify errors and their causes.

Figure 2. Possibilities of using elements of robotics in the educational process

In addition, the use of the Arduino platform in teaching solar panels, as we can see in Figure 2, is an effective way to give students an idea of renewable energy sources and their operating principles. Through the Arduino platform, students learn to explore and operate solar panels, making the learning process interactive and experiential. The Arduino platform plays a fundamental role in the assembly and control of robots. It combines all the components of the robot and ensures that they work.

Students connect the solar panel to the Arduino platform and get acquainted with the necessary tools to monitor its operation, such as a solar panel, voltage and current sensors, light sensors (for example, LDR - a light-dependent resistor). Students write code in the Ar-

duino IDE programming environment and develop programming skills to control solar panel operation and collect data (Write a code to measure the voltage and current of the solar panel. Changing the angle of the solar panel through light sensors and finding the most advantageous position).

M. Kandlhofer examines the possibilities of robotics in the process of teaching gifted students in high school on the example of MINT-Robo, which aims to develop skills in the field of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Conducted in the form of interactive seminars, laboratory work and practical classes aimed at developing and programming educational robots. As a result of the study, students participating in the MINT-Robo project show a significant

improvement in academic performance and motivation for STEM education [5].

Arduino Robotics projects help students understand the basics of programming and electronics. This educational method allows students to acquire practical skills:

STEM education - Arduino Robotics is used in teaching STEM subjects (science, technology, engineering, mathematics);

Experimental laboratories - allows students to develop practical projects and explore them through the Arduino platform.

Therefore, the connection between Arduino and robotics will help students master the skills of assembling and programming robots. This method allows you to develop the technical and creative abilities of students, as well as deepen their knowledge in the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering and mathematics (STEM).

Conclusion

Teaching movement in a circle using Lego robotics allows students to understand physical concepts in practice and apply them in practice. This method can increase students' interest and help them develop creativity, critical thinking, and technical skills.

Teaching solar panels using the Arduino platform helps students understand renewable energy sources and their operating principles. This method allows students to develop practical, programming and creativity skills, and also encourages them to pay attention to the issues of efficient energy use and Environmental Protection.

The relationship between Arduino and robotics is very close, as the Arduino platform is widely used to control and program various components of robots. The Arduino microcontroller establishes a connection between the sensors, motors and other devices of the robots, ensuring that they work in harmony.

The interdisciplinary continuity of STEM in physics contributed to the comprehensive development of students, their acquisition of scientific and technical skills, as well as future professional training. This method made the learning process interesting, interactive and productive.

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